

Land Use Transformations Project (JHI-C3-1)

Milestone 30 – Topic Policy Day

Internal Note

Versions, first complete 27/3/2024

This milestone was holding a meeting with Scottish Government policy and analysis staff. The meeting was held via Teams with the presentations stored on the project website.

End of Year Presentations, 2023-24:

1. [Overview](#) - Keith Matthews
2. [Climate and Soils](#) - Mike Rivington
3. [Land Use Change Scenarios](#) - Alessandro Gimona
4. [Peat Condition Mapping](#) - Matt Aitkenhead (presented by Fraser McFarlane).
5. [Governance](#) - Kirsty Blackstock
6. [Story Telling](#) – Naomi Beingessner
7. [Enhanced Conditionality](#) - Keith Matthews

The James Hutton Institute is supported by the Scottish Government’s Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services Division (RESAS). Research funded through grant JHI-C3-1 and previous Strategic Research Programmes.

